

Translated Filipino Versions of Regional Songs and Cultural Reception of Diverse Grade 7 Learners in Isulan

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Publication Date: May 23, 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15522601

Abstract

Understanding how translated Filipino versions of regional songs shape cultural reception is essential for promoting inclusivity, preserving cultural heritage, and reinforcing the connection between language and identity in diverse learning environments. This study investigated the cultural reception of Filipino-translated regional songs among Grade 7 learners in Isulan, employing a Sequential Explanatory Mixed-Methods Research Design. The research aimed to evaluate how these translations influence students' cultural appreciation, comprehension, and inclusivity across varied ethnolinguistic backgrounds. Results showed a high level of acceptability and a positive reception toward the translated songs. Learners perceived the translations as authentic and meaningful, effectively preserving the original emotional depth, cultural essence, and regional identity of the songs. The use of Filipino as a shared language facilitated inclusive participation and

equitable cultural engagement, demonstrating the potential of translanguaging practices in educational contexts. Three key factors emerged as central to this positive reception: enhanced comprehension through translation, retention of original musical elements that ensured emotional resonance, and the fostering of inclusivity through a common linguistic medium. While learners acknowledged the cultural integrity of the translations, some recommended further refinement for improved clarity and emotional impact. Based on these findings, the study advocates for the integration of translated regional songs into classroom instruction and school-based cultural programs. It further recommends collaboration with local artists and cultural practitioners to ensure authenticity, and the use of interactive, culturally responsive teaching strategies to deepen student engagement and understanding.

Keywords: *Translated Filipino Versions, Regional Songs, Cultural Reception, Diverse Learners, Music*

INTRODUCTION

The cultural heritage of a nation defines its people, playing a significant role in cultural identification, identity formation, and the creation of social bonds within specific communities. Music and traditional songs are integral to cultural heritage and are a significant part of Filipino culture, reflecting the nation's rich diversity. These songs serve as vehicles for storytelling, cultural expression, and social connection. Filipino music encompasses various genres including folk songs, chants, lullabies, and contemporary styles each illustrating the nation's multicultural roots across over 7,000 islands, with distinct ethnic groups, dialects, and traditions.

Modernization and globalization continue to threaten the survival of indigenous cultures, leading to the erosion of traditional knowledge and practices. In response, global efforts such as UNESCO's initiatives to safeguard intangible cultural heritage have emphasized the importance of oral traditions and traditional music in maintaining cultural identity (The New Yorker, 2023). Music education has emerged as a vital strategy in this preservation, as it enables learners to engage with their cultural heritage while promoting inclusivity and a sense of identity. Integrating folk and traditional music into educational settings not only reinforces cultural values but also fosters inclusive learning environments for students from diverse backgrounds (NAfME, 2023).

Indigenous Filipino cultures exhibit diverse ways of life, with oral traditions contributing to a growing sense of nationalism. These traditions serve as repositories of artistic expression and styles that can be utilized in contemporary literature and education but they are rapidly disappearing. Recognizing this threat, the National Commission on Culture and the Arts (NCCA), mandated by Republic Act No. 7356, has emphasized the urgent need for regional cultural preservation (Republic Act No. 7356, 1992).

The MATATAG K to 10 Curriculum integrates music and arts education to foster cultural appreciation, with the Grade 7 program emphasizing connections between Philippine and Southeast Asian traditions (Department of Education, 2023). Folk songs, in particular, serve as effective tools for helping students connect with their cultural roots. However, successful integration depends on accurate translation that preserves the original meaning and cultural essence. As Yale University Press (2016) highlights, translation plays a vital role in expanding cross-cultural understanding by allowing individuals to access the emotions, perspectives, and experiences embedded in diverse cultural narratives.

Furthermore, Article XIV, Section 6 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution states that Filipino is the national language of the Philippines and must continue to develop based on existing Philippine and other languages. Translating regional songs into Filipino the country's most widely spoken language facilitates better comprehension and appreciation. A Filipino translation allows a broader audience to understand the song's meaning while enriching their knowledge of the language. Since many young learners are more exposed to Filipino than to native dialects, translated versions can enhance cultural literacy and ensure that traditional songs remain relevant to future generations.

Culturally relevant pedagogy plays a crucial role in fostering inclusive education among diverse learners. As highlighted by Lupas (2023), programs such as the one at Isulan Central School demonstrate how incorporating cultural heritage into instruction can support equity and responsiveness in education. This approach aligns with both the K to 12 Basic Education Program in the Philippines and global frameworks advocating for inclusive, identity-affirming curricula (Gay, 2018; UNESCO, 2021). Translating regional songs into Filipino enables students from varied cultural backgrounds to connect with their heritage, reinforcing cultural identity while cultivating an inclusive and ethnolinguistically responsive classroom environment.

Thus, this study is essential in assessing the acceptability and cultural reception of translated Filipino versions of regional songs among Grade 7 learners in Isulan. It seeks to determine whether translation enhances cultural appreciation, familiarity, and perceived authenticity while maintaining the original cultural essence of these musical pieces. Through this research, valuable insights can be gained into how young learners engage with their cultural heritage and the role of translation in preserving traditional music for future generations.

METHODS

Research Design

This study adopted a **Sequential Explanatory Mixed-Methods Research Design**, consisting of two distinct phases: a quantitative phase followed by a qualitative phase. The initial phase involved the collection of numerical data using structured survey questionnaires to assess the **acceptability and cultural reception** of the translated Filipino versions of regional songs. The quantitative results focused on how students from diverse linguistic and

cultural backgrounds evaluated the **accuracy, appropriateness, and cultural tone** of the translations. In the second phase, **qualitative data** were gathered through in-depth interviews and **focus group discussions (FGDs)** to further explore learners' perspectives on the effectiveness of the translations in preserving the cultural essence of the original songs. Expert evaluators were also consulted to assess the **artistic and emotional fidelity** of the translations, adding further rigor to the interpretation of findings. The choice of a Sequential Explanatory Design was guided by Creswell (2015), who highlighted that **mixed-method research** enhances the **validity and reliability** of findings by combining the strengths of both quantitative and qualitative approaches.

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in three public secondary schools in the municipality of **Isulan, Sultan Kudarat: Isulan National High School, Bambad National High School, and Laguilayan National High School**. These schools were selected due to their culturally diverse student populations, representing Indigenous Peoples (IPs), Moro communities, and Christian settlers. This made them ideal settings for examining how students from different cultural and linguistic backgrounds received and interpreted translated regional songs.

Respondents of the Study

A total of **300 Grade 7 students** from the three identified schools participated in the study: 200 from Isulan National High School, 60 from Bambad National High School, and 40 from Laguilayan National High School. These respondents were chosen as they were studying regional songs under the **MATATAG K to 10 Curriculum**, which emphasizes local music and cultural heritage. Grade 7 students were ideal respondents due to their curricular exposure to **Philippine folk songs** and Southeast Asian musical traditions. At this developmental stage, students begin forming cultural awareness, and their responses provided key insights into how translated regional songs influence their understanding of **cultural identity and diversity**.

Sampling Technique

The study employed **stratified random sampling** for the quantitative phase and **purposive sampling** for the qualitative phase. For the quantitative phase, **Yamane's formula** was used to determine the appropriate sample size, ensuring proportional representation across the schools. Stratification was based on school enrollment, and a **fishbowl method** was used to randomly select participants within each stratum. For the qualitative phase, **10 students** were purposively selected based on their cultural background, musical exposure, and survey responses. An open call for volunteers was conducted, and students from IPs, Moro, and Christian communities with distinct responses to the survey were included. Parental consent was secured for their participation in interviews and FGDs.

Data Gathering Instruments

The study used two primary survey instruments developed by the researcher. The first instrument assessed **acceptability**, focusing on **accuracy, appropriateness, and cultural tone** of the translated songs, rated using a **Five-Point Likert Scale**. This was completed by expert evaluators. The second instrument, designed for student respondents, included three parts: (1) demographic profile, (2) cultural reception of translated songs in terms of appreciation, familiarity, and perceived authenticity, and (3) unstructured questions for interviews and FGDs. The same Likert scale format was applied for consistency and clarity. To ensure the instruments' **validity**, they were reviewed by a panel of experts, including the advisory committee, a language critic, and technical validators. Using the **Content Validity Index (CVI)**, both I-CVI and S-CVI values were recorded at **1.00**, indicating excellent validity based on Yusoff's (2019) standard for a small expert panel. Instrument **reliability** was tested using **Cronbach's Alpha**, with a coefficient of **0.86**, surpassing the acceptable threshold of 0.70 (Wells & Wollack, 2003), thus demonstrating strong internal consistency.

Data Gathering Procedure

The data collection followed a structured and ethical process. After obtaining approval from the advisory committee, school officials, and ethics review boards, the regional songs were translated into Filipino. The instruments were developed, validated, and pilot-tested with a small group of students to refine the items. Survey questionnaires were distributed to 300 randomly selected Grade 7 students, with instructions and informed consent procedures explained beforehand. For the qualitative phase, selected students participated in in-depth interviews and FGDs. Consent from parents was secured, and sessions were recorded, transcribed, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

Quantitative data were analyzed using **mean** and **standard deviation** for the first two research questions, which explored acceptability and cultural reception. These measures indicated the average level of agreement and the variability of student responses. To examine differences in cultural reception across cultural groups, a **Two-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)** was employed, analyzing the interaction between learners’ cultural backgrounds and the type of translated song. Qualitative data from interviews and FGDs were subjected to **thematic analysis**, identifying recurring patterns and deeper insights into learners’ experiences and perceptions of cultural authenticity in the translated songs.

Ethical Considerations

The study upheld high ethical standards. **Informed consent** was obtained from parents or guardians, and **verbal assent** from students. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw at any point without penalty. Confidentiality was maintained using pseudonyms and secured data storage. Only validated and culturally appropriate songs were used to minimize risk. Cultural respect was integral throughout the study, with translation experts consulted to preserve the integrity of the original compositions. No group or culture was misrepresented. **Voluntary participation** and ethical clearance from relevant authorities were strictly observed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Summary Level of Acceptability of the Translated Filipino Versions of Regional Songs

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
1. Accuracy	4.58	0.01	Very High
2. Appropriateness	4.62	0.02	Very High
3. Preservation of Cultural Tones	4.63	0.05	Very High
Grand Mean	4.61	0.07	Very High

The table 1 shows that the overall results indicate the **translated Filipino versions of regional songs** achieved a **Very High** level of acceptability, as reflected in the **grand mean of 4.61**. Among the three components, **Accuracy** received a rating of **(4.58)**, suggesting that the translations effectively preserved the regional songs' original meaning, essence, and intent. **Appropriateness (4.62)** and **Preservation of Cultural Tones (4.63)** also garnered very high ratings, indicating that the translations maintained cultural relevance, used language suitable for the intended audience, and successfully conveyed the regional identity and traditions of the original songs. These findings affirm that the translated versions facilitate linguistic comprehension and uphold cultural authenticity, making them well-received and suitable for diverse audiences. The study by Pamarta (2022) supports the present findings by emphasizing that accuracy and appropriateness are crucial factors in determining the acceptability of song translations. It highlights how maintaining fidelity to the original lyrics and ensuring cultural relevance contribute to audience engagement and comprehension, reinforcing the significance of these elements in the translation of regional songs.

Table 2. Summary Level of Cultural Reception of the Translated Filipino Versions of Regional Songs among Diverse Learners in Isulan

Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description
Appreciation	4.46	Strongly Agree
Familiarity	4.47	Strongly Agree
Perceived Authenticity	4.52	Strongly Agree
Grand Mean	4.48	Strongly Agree

Table 2 presents the summary level of cultural reception of the translated Filipino versions of regional songs among diverse learners in Isulan. The overall mean score for the three components combined is 4.48, corresponding to Strongly Agree. This indicates a generally high cultural reception among the diverse learners in Isulan toward the translated Filipino versions of regional songs. The results reflect the effectiveness of these translations in promoting

cultural understanding, appreciation, and authenticity. These results are consistent with existing literature on the role of translation in enhancing cultural reception and authenticity in music education. For instance, Reyes (2019) highlighted that translating songs in children's films enhances cultural understanding and appreciation among young audiences. The translated songs enabled learners to comprehend better and enjoy the content, which, in turn, fostered a stronger connection to the cultural messages conveyed through the music. Similarly, Zhuang (2022) emphasized the importance of maintaining cultural authenticity when teaching world music in multicultural settings. Zhuang found that when educators present music sensitively to a cultural context, students demonstrate more meaningful engagement and appreciation.

Table 3. Significant Difference in the Cultural Reception of Translated Filipino Regional Songs Among Diverse Grade 7 Learners in Terms of Appreciation.

Appreciation	Ilocano		Ilonggo		Maguindanaon		Others	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SONG 1	4.64 ^a	0.31	4.37 ^b	0.47	4.38 ^b	0.45	4.45 ^b	0.43
SONG 2	4.64 ^a	0.34	4.50 ^a	0.46	4.32 ^b	0.50	4.59 ^a	0.38
SONG 3	4.51 ^a	0.50	4.44 ^a	0.49	4.46 ^a	0.53	4.52 ^a	0.49
p(row)	0.06							
p(column)	<0.05							

Table 3 presents the cultural reception of the translated Filipino versions of regional songs among diverse learners in Isulan, in terms of Appreciation. Results revealed a significant difference in the cultural reception of Song 1, $p < .05$, with Ilocano students exhibiting a higher reception level than other groups. This finding suggests that cultural proximity and familiarity may influence learners' reception of regional songs, even when translated into Filipino. Learners who share cultural ties with the region of origin or have greater exposure to similar cultural elements may find the song more relatable and meaningful. This underscores the importance of considering learners' cultural backgrounds when selecting instructional materials and promoting cultural content in education. Similarly, a significant difference was found in the cultural reception of Song 2, $p < .05$. Ilocano, Ilonggo, and students from other ethnolinguistic groups demonstrated comparable reception levels, which were significantly higher than those reported by Maguindanaon students. This variation in cultural reception may reflect differences in cultural representation, language familiarity, or the perceived relevance of the song's themes to the different cultural groups. In contrast, there was no significant difference in the cultural reception of Song 3 among learners with varying cultural backgrounds, $p > .05$. The perceptions of all groups were comparable, suggesting that some regional songs, when thoughtfully translated, may transcend cultural boundaries and foster a shared appreciation across diverse learners. This finding indicates that the translated version of Song 3 may have achieved a universal appeal, effectively bridging cultural differences among the learners. Overall, the perceptions of all groups concerning the three songs were comparable ($p = .06$) despite some differences in individual song reception. This suggests that the translated Filipino versions of regional songs promote cultural inclusivity and mutual appreciation among diverse learners. This aligns with research on culturally responsive teaching, emphasizing that incorporating students' cultural customs and lived experiences into instructional materials makes learning more meaningful and engaging (Domzalski, 2022).

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Cultural Reception of Translated Filipino Regional Songs Among Diverse Grade 7 Learners in terms of Familiarity

Familiarity	Ilocano		Ilonggo		Maguindanaon		Others	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SONG 1	4.57 ^a	0.40	4.33 ^b	0.54	4.44 ^a	0.50	4.48 ^a	0.43
SONG 2	4.71 ^a	0.34	4.51 ^b	0.43	4.41 ^b	0.51	4.56 ^{a,b}	0.40
SONG 3	4.47 ^a	0.54	4.43 ^a	0.50	4.57 ^a	0.41	4.53 ^a	0.48
p(row)	0.06							
p(column)	<0.05							

Table 4 presents the significant differences in the cultural reception of the translated Filipino regional songs among diverse Grade 7 learners in terms of familiarity. The analysis revealed a significant difference in the cultural

reception of Song 1 among learners with varying cultural backgrounds ($p < .05$). Specifically, Ilocano students demonstrated a higher level of familiarity and reception ($M = 4.57, SD = 0.40$) compared to Ilonggo students ($M = 4.33, SD = 0.54$). However, their level of reception was comparable to Maguindanaon ($M = 4.44, SD = 0.50$) and Other students ($M = 4.48, SD = 0.43$). This suggests that Ilocano students may have greater cultural familiarity with Song 1, which could have contributed to their higher level of reception. Similarly, there was a significant difference in the cultural reception of Song 2 among the different cultural groups ($p < .05$). Ilocano students reported the highest level of reception ($M = 4.71, SD = 0.34$), comparable to Other students ($M = 4.56, SD = 0.40$). However, the reception of Ilocano students was significantly higher than that of Ilonggo ($M = 4.51, SD = 0.43$) and Maguindanaon students ($M = 4.41, SD = 0.51$). This indicates that both Ilocano and Other students found Song 2 more familiar and culturally resonant, which may explain their higher reception levels. In contrast, no significant difference was found in the cultural reception of Song 3 among learners from different cultural backgrounds ($p > .05$). Ilocano ($M = 4.47, SD = 0.54$), Ilonggo ($M = 4.43, SD = 0.50$), Maguindanaon ($M = 4.57, SD = 0.41$), and Other students ($M = 4.53, SD = 0.48$) exhibited comparable levels of reception. This suggests that Song 3 may have a more universal appeal or that its translation effectively bridges cultural differences, making it equally familiar and acceptable to all groups. Overall, comparing the cultural reception of all three songs across the different cultural groups resulted in a p -value of .06, indicating no significant difference in their collective perceptions. Despite individual differences for Songs 1 and 2, this overall result implies a general trend towards comparable levels of familiarity and reception across cultural groups. The findings of this study suggest that learners' cultural backgrounds significantly influence their familiarity with and reception of translated Filipino regional songs. Specifically, Ilocano students exhibited higher familiarity and reception for certain songs compared to Ilonggo and Maguindanaon learners. Likewise, Büdenbender and Kreutz (2016) explored how national culture influences the familiarity of Western melodies. Their research indicates that individuals from different cultural backgrounds perceive and process musical elements differently, affecting their recognition and appreciation of melodies.

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Cultural Reception of Translated Filipino Regional Songs Among Diverse Grade 7 Learners in terms of Perceived Authenticity

Perceived Authenticity	Ilocano		Ilonggo		Mag		Others	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
SONG 1	4.61 ^a	0.37	4.46 ^b	0.42	4.52 ^a	0.41	4.50 ^a	0.40
SONG 2	4.66 ^a	0.30	4.53 ^{a,b}	0.41	4.48 ^b	0.48	4.60 ^{a,b}	0.44
SONG 3	4.55 ^a	0.45	4.48 ^a	0.45	4.59 ^a	0.39	4.54 ^a	0.45
p(row)	0.06							
p(column)	<0.05							

Table 5 presents the significant differences in the cultural reception of the translated Filipino regional songs among diverse Grade 7 learners regarding perceived authenticity. The analysis revealed a significant difference in the cultural reception of Song 1 among learners with varying cultural backgrounds ($p < .05$). Ilocano students demonstrated a higher level of perceived authenticity ($M = 4.61, SD = 0.37$) compared to Ilonggo students ($M = 4.46, SD = 0.42$). At the same time, their perceptions were comparable to those of Maguindanaon ($M = 4.52, SD = 0.41$) and Other students ($M = 4.50, SD = 0.40$). This suggests that Ilocano students may have found Song 1 more culturally authentic, likely due to cultural proximity or familiarity with the song's thematic elements and musical style. A significant difference was also found in the cultural reception of Song 2 ($p < .05$). Ilocano students ($M = 4.66, SD = 0.30$), Ilonggo students ($M = 4.53, SD = 0.41$), and Other students ($M = 4.60, SD = 0.44$) reported comparable levels of perceived authenticity. However, their ratings were significantly higher than those of Maguindanaon students ($M = 4.48, SD = 0.48$). This result indicates that Song 2 was perceived as more authentic by learners from Ilocano, Ilonggo, and Other cultural backgrounds, potentially reflecting greater familiarity or relevance to these groups' cultural experiences. In contrast, there was no significant difference in the perceived authenticity of Song 3 across cultural groups ($p > .05$). Ilocano ($M = 4.55, SD = 0.45$), Ilonggo ($M = 4.48, SD = 0.45$), Maguindanaon ($M = 4.59, SD = 0.39$), and Other students ($M = 4.54, SD = 0.45$) reported comparable levels of reception. This suggests that Song 3 may possess universal appeal or that its translation effectively conveys authenticity to learners from various cultural backgrounds. Overall, the perceptions of all groups concerning all three songs were comparable, with a p -value of .06. Although individual differences were noted. The overall results for Songs 1 and 2 indicate that the translated Filipino regional songs generally promote consistent perceptions of authenticity among learners from different cultural

backgrounds. This study conforms with existing research on cultural proximity and music perception. Trehub, Becker, and Morley (2015) highlight that while musical behaviors are universal, they are also highly diverse in their structures, roles, and interpretations, deeply influenced by cultural experiences.

Table 6. Emerging Themes on the Factors Influencing Learners' Appreciation and Reception of the Translated Filipino Regional Songs

Theme	Core Ideas
1. Enhanced Comprehension through Translation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translation into Filipino made lyrics more accessible across ethnolinguistic groups • Learners better understood song messages and themes • Facilitated deeper cognitive and emotional connections • Promoted inclusive learning regardless of mother tongue
2. Preservation of Musical Authenticity and Emotional Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Original melody, rhythm, and tone were preserved • Emotional resonance maintained despite translation • Musical enjoyment enhanced engagement • Authentic delivery retained cultural meaning and experience
3. Cultural Inclusivity and Neutrality through Common Language	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filipino functioned as a culturally neutral and inclusive medium • Broadened acceptance of songs from different regions • Encouraged shared appreciation and minimized cultural bias • Unified learners from diverse cultural backgrounds

Table 6 outlines the key themes that emerged from the analysis of learners' responses concerning their appreciation and reception of regional songs translated into Filipino.

One of the most prominent themes from the interviews was the **enhanced comprehension** brought about by translating regional songs into Filipino. Participants expressed that understanding the lyrics in Filipino made it easier for them to appreciate the songs' messages. The findings of this study reveal that the translation of regional songs into Filipino significantly enhanced learners' comprehension and appreciation, regardless of their linguistic backgrounds. This observation aligns with Reyes (2019), who emphasized that using familiar languages in instruction allows Filipino learners to access knowledge more effectively. Another significant theme is the **preservation of musical authenticity and emotional impact** despite the language translation. Several participants noted that while the lyrics changed, the melody and tone remained faithful to the original, which helped maintain the emotional connection to the song. This observation is supported by Schindler et al. (2017), who emphasized that maintaining authenticity in key musical components, such as melody and tone, is essential for preserving listeners' emotional connections with music, even when lyrics undergo translation. Their study demonstrates that cultural and personal perceptions of authenticity can influence how music is cognitively processed and emotionally experienced. The third theme centers on **cultural inclusivity and neutrality**, which is made possible by using Filipino as a common language for translation. Participants conveyed that translating regional songs into Filipino made them easier to accept and appreciate, regardless of cultural background. Recent studies continue to highlight how using a common language in multicultural music education plays a key role in bringing students together and helping them connect across cultural lines. For example, Liu (2024) points out that when teachers use language that everyone can understand, it makes it easier for students to engage with and appreciate music from different cultures. This kind of inclusive approach allows students from all backgrounds to feel seen and involved in the learning process. In the same way, Yoo (2023) shares how teaching both traditional and modern versions of diverse musical pieces while keeping the meaning and cultural value intact helps students relate more deeply to the music.

Table 7. Emerging Themes on the Effectiveness of Translation in Preserving the Original Cultural Essence of Songs

Theme	Core Ideas
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1. Preservation of Cultural Essence Through Faithful Translation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Translations maintained the original spirit, tone, and message of the songs. • Learners still felt the provincial or cultural atmosphere even when the language was changed. • Changes were limited to words, not meaning or emotional impact. • Emotional and cultural identity remained intact and recognizable across languages.
2. Language Accessibility for Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Filipino translations made the songs easier to understand for students from different ethnic or language backgrounds. • Helped bridge comprehension gaps for those unfamiliar with the original regional languages. • Promoted inclusive learning and better emotional connection through shared understanding.
3. Minimal Loss in Meaning but Suggestions for Simplicity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Majority felt that the core meaning remained, but some noted use of deep or unfamiliar words. • Learners preferred simplified vocabulary to aid clarity and understanding. • Translation quality could be improved by balancing accuracy with simplicity. • Translated songs enabled cultural exchange beyond local or regional boundaries.
4. Translation as a Tool for Cultural Inclusion and Unity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Songs in Filipino were seen as tools for national unity and shared heritage. • Translation fostered intercultural appreciation and reduced exclusivity of regional content.
5. Need for Continuous Improvement in Translation Quality	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Learners acknowledged the positive impact of translation but called for better skill development among translators. • Emphasis on refinement of translation practices to boost accessibility, emotional depth, and accuracy. • Improved translations would allow more people to relate to and enjoy the songs.

The table 7 presents the five emerging themes derived from the thematic analysis of learners' responses regarding the effectiveness of translating regional songs into Filipino. These themes reflect the learners' perceptions of how translation influences the preservation of cultural identity, comprehension, and inclusivity. The data highlights not only the strengths of translation in retaining the original spirit and meaning of the songs but also areas that call for improvement, particularly in enhancing clarity and emotional resonance.

Thematic analysis of the learners' responses revealed five major themes regarding the effectiveness of translating regional songs into Filipino. First, there is a strong consensus on preserving cultural essence through faithful translation. Learners emphasized that the original spirit, message, and tone were maintained despite translating regional songs into Filipino.

The findings of this study highlight that the learners perceived the translated regional songs as retaining their original cultural essence. Despite the language change, participants consistently expressed that the songs' message, tone, and spirit were preserved. This perception aligns with House's (2015) assertion that high-quality translations maintain the semantic and cultural fidelity of the source material.

Secondly, the theme of language accessibility for understanding emerged clearly. Participants appreciated that translating the songs into Filipino allowed people from various linguistic backgrounds to comprehend the message better.

The findings of this study revealed that translating regional songs into Filipino significantly enhanced the learners' comprehension, making the songs more accessible to students from diverse linguistic backgrounds. Participants consistently noted that the use of Filipino allowed them to understand the message of the songs better, even if they did not belong to the region or speak the original language.

This observation is supported by UNESCO (2016), which emphasizes that instruction delivered in a language familiar to learners reduces barriers to understanding and promotes inclusivity in education. Similarly, Reyes (2019) highlights the effectiveness of mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) in bridging linguistic gaps, arguing that instruction in a common language fosters participation and comprehension in multilingual settings.

The third theme involves minimal loss in meaning but suggestions for simplicity. While most learners stated that nothing significant was lost in the translation, some pointed out that complex or deep words could confuse listeners.

This observation aligns with House's (2015) emphasis on clarity and simplicity as critical indicators of high-quality translation, particularly in cross-cultural and educational contexts.

A fourth theme that emerged is translation as a tool for cultural inclusion and unity. Participants believe that translating regional songs into Filipino helps bridge cultural divides and promotes a shared understanding of cultural heritage.

The findings of this study reveal that learners perceive the translation of regional songs into Filipino as an effective means of promoting cultural inclusion and unity. Participants shared that translating songs enables them to transcend linguistic and cultural barriers, allowing individuals from different ethnolinguistic groups to appreciate the meaning and cultural significance embedded in the songs.

Recent research underscores the critical importance of continuous improvement in translation quality to ensure cultural sensitivity and effective communication. For instance, Jiang and Murugesan (2024) emphasize that enhancing translators' skills is crucial for maintaining semantic and cultural fidelity in translations, particularly between English and Chinese. Their study highlights the necessity of ongoing training to effectively address linguistic nuances and cultural contexts. Additionally, the Translators Report (2023) discusses the implementation of quality assurance measures, such as translation memory tools and glossaries, to improve translation consistency and cultural appropriateness. The report stresses that continuous learning and the adoption of quality control processes are vital for translators to deliver accurate and culturally sensitive translations.

Lastly, learners highlighted the need for continuous improvement in translation quality. While most were satisfied with the translations, they recognized that refining translators' skills could further enhance the accuracy and emotional resonance of the songs.

Recent studies underscore the importance of continuous improvement in translation quality to ensure cultural sensitivity and effective communication. Jiang and Murugesan (2024) emphasize that enhancing translators' skills is essential for maintaining both semantic and cultural fidelity in translations, particularly in contexts involving linguistically and culturally diverse languages such as English and Chinese. Their research demonstrates that ongoing training is necessary for translators to navigate linguistic nuances and convey culturally embedded meanings effectively.

Conclusion

The following conclusions are drawn in light of the findings:

There was a high acceptability of translated Filipino versions of regional songs among diverse learners. These translations effectively preserved the original meaning, cultural essence, and emotional depth, ensuring accuracy and relevance. They foster cultural understanding, appreciation, and inclusivity by conveying regional identity and traditions. The strong consensus on their quality and authenticity highlights their value as educational tools for promoting linguistic comprehension and preserving cultural heritage.

The translated Filipino versions of regional songs effectively fostered a high cultural reception among diverse learners in Isulan. The songs were perceived as authentic, familiar, and meaningful, highlighting their role in preserving cultural integrity and promoting deeper appreciation and connection to regional traditions and identities. These findings underscore the value of translation as a tool for enhancing cultural understanding and engagement among learners.

Further, cultural background significantly influences learners' reception of translated Filipino regional songs. Ilocano students exhibited stronger familiarity, perceived authenticity, and overall appreciation, highlighting the role

of cultural proximity and prior exposure in shaping their engagement. While some songs resonated more with specific groups, one translation successfully bridged cultural differences, fostering inclusivity. These findings emphasize the importance of culturally adaptive translations in promoting appreciation and understanding among diverse learners.

The Grade 7 learners' appreciation and reception of translated Filipino versions of regional songs are significantly influenced by three interrelated factors: improved comprehension through Filipino translations, the preservation of original musical elements ensuring emotional resonance, and the inclusivity of using a common language. Together, these factors highlight the potential of translated regional songs as effective educational tools for promoting cultural appreciation, understanding, and unity among learners from diverse backgrounds.

Lastly, the learners collectively described the translation of regional songs into Filipino as effective in preserving the original cultural essence, making the songs accessible to a wider audience, and fostering cultural inclusion. While the essence was maintained, they acknowledged that translation efforts could be improved through simplification and refinement to maximize clarity and emotional impact.

Recommendations

Upon thorough study and interpretation of the data, the following recommendations were made:

Teachers may integrate translated Filipino versions of regional songs into classroom instruction and school activities to enhance cultural awareness, linguistic comprehension, and appreciation of regional heritage. Collaboration with local artists and cultural experts may be encouraged to ensure the authenticity of future translations.

Teachers may integrate translated regional songs into the music and cultural education curriculum. Doing so may further enhance students' cultural awareness, appreciation, and connection to the country's diverse heritage.

Teachers may be encouraged to design interactive activities, such as reflective discussions or cultural exchange sessions, where students may share personal interpretations and experiences related to the translated regional songs. This may deepen cultural understanding, encourage meaningful dialogue, and strengthen the shared appreciation observed in the study.

It is recommended that DepEd may include translated Filipino versions of regional songs in the Music and Arts curriculum to promote cultural inclusivity in schools. Teachers may also be given training and materials to ensure the translations remain accurate and respectful of the original culture.

It is recommended that simplified, learner-friendly versions of translated regional songs may be developed, accompanied by learning guides or contextual materials that explain the song's cultural background, to enhance students' understanding and appreciation during classroom activities.

Future researchers may be encouraged to conduct longitudinal studies to examine the long-term impact of integrating translated regional songs into the curriculum on students' cultural identity, musical skills, and intercultural understanding. This may provide deeper insights into how sustained exposure to culturally diverse musical content influences learners' attitudes and values.

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